

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

LINGUOPRAGMATIC FEATURES OF ENGLISH DOCUMENTATION IN THE CUSTOMS SPHERE

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Abstract

The article reveals the necessity of study of linguopragmatic features of English documentation in the customs sphere because with the development of international relations, trade between Ukraine and foreign countries has increased. Customs clearance of goods is carried out in accordance with the norms of Ukrainian legislation, all necessary documents are drawn up in the Ukrainian language. Therefore, the role of the translation of customs documents is constantly growing and requires a detailed study of the linguistic and pragmatic aspects of the translation of customs texts.

Key words: linguistic, customs documentation, regulatory documents, stylistic features

It is worth noting that an important component of translation is language design. The structure of the text also depends on its stylistic and genre features. For example, an article, report, or official document may differ both in translation and in design of the text in different languages. Therefore, in order to understand the linguistic and pragmatic features of the translation of English-language customs documentation, it is worth outlining its genre and stylistic features.

Customs documents belong to the official-business style. Their purpose is to establish cooperation between two or more parties, which may be represented by the state, individual or legal entity, companies, organizations, enterprises, etc. They are aimed at regulating legal relations between business entities at the level of foreign economic relations [4].

Customs documents are necessary to confirm the legal movement of goods across the customs border, as well as the legality of trade transactions. They must provide accurate, truthful and comprehensive information about manufacturers, products and their characteristics, suppliers and buyers. These are documents such as: Customs Declaration, Export, Import and Exchange Permits, Certificate of Origin, Consular Invoice, Transit documents Documents), veterinary, sanitary and quarantine certificates, quality certificates, documents providing preferential taxation (Documents for Customs Clearance) , Insurance Certificate, Invoice, Proforma Invoice, etc.

A. Abdullaeva points out that the main customs documents are cargo customs declaration, licenses, declaration of customs value, cargo documents, etc. [1].

Researcher A. Svetlichna presents the following genre system of the complex of English-language customs documents [5]:

- declarations – passenger Customs Declaration, Cargo/Goods Declaration;
- certificates – Certificate of Origin, Certificate of Quality, Weight List, Phytosanitary Certificate;
- commercial documents – Invoice, Proforma-Invoice;
- customs documents providing preferential taxation - ATA carnet ATA Carnet.

These documents are presented as specific forms and contain mandatory elements that must be filled in by participants in foreign economic relations. The style and language of presentation of mandatory and variable components are the same because they are designed to fulfill a single unambiguous communicative purpose.

According to N. Berestetska's research on the peculiarities of the border discourse, administrative documents regulate the professional behavior of officials [2]. In our opinion, customs documents have the same impact, since they are directly related to border activities, and the term system of the customs sphere has borrowed part of border terms.

According to the scientific investigations of the researcher K. Luth, among the general stylistic characteristics characteristic of customs documentation, one can single out consistency, accuracy, clarity, clarity and conciseness of information, standard, neutral presentation, lack of ambiguity, imagery, emotionality and individual authorial elements. Codes, numbers, and standards are often used in such documents [4]. Example:

Identify all regulatory requirements that effect a freight container (49 CFR parts 450-453, 49 CFR 173.411(b)(6)) (Freight Container Guidance Document, 2014).

«429 BALES», «GROSS: 25589.20KGS» (Weight List).

All these characteristics contribute not only to the effectiveness of customs control, but also to legal regulation. The structure of the texts is also always clear. The mandatory component is represented by details located in a certain sequence, which facilitates perception and simplifies their processing by control authorities: the document number, who issued it, its validity period, the purpose for which the cargo crosses the border, etc.:

«ATA Carnet № », «Issued by», «Valid until», «Intended use of goods»

«Family name _____
First (Given) _____ Middle _____»

[5]

The number and set of components are not the same and depend on the type of document and its purpose, but a signature is an integral part of any document, as it certifies its authenticity and makes it legal. For clearer organization, the text is divided into paragraphs, sections and paragraphs [4]:

Authorized packagings. A packaging is authorized for a hazardous material only if –

(1) The packaging is prescribed or permitted for the hazardous material in a packaging section specified for that material in Column 8 of the Sec. 172.101 table and conforms to applicable requirements in the special provisions of Column 7 of the Sec. 172.101 table and, for specification packagings (but not including UN standard packagings manufactured outside the United States), the specification requirements in parts 178 and 179 of this subchapter; or

(2) The packaging is permitted under, and conforms to, provisions contained in subparts B or C of part 171 of this subchapter or Sections 173.3, 173.4, 173.4a, 173.4b, 173.5, 173.5a, 173.6, 173.7, 173.8, 173.27, or Section 176.11 of this subchapter (Freight Container Guidance Document, 2014).

Researcher A. Svetlichna emphasizes that present tense forms are often used in English customs documentation, which is due to the need to obtain specific facts necessary for the customs process. In addition, verbs are common in the texts of English customs documents. They make it possible to obtain a unified grammatical design of situations related to customs processes, to have an appropriate influence on the recipient, to formulate additional information about the subject or person as concisely as possible, avoiding complex phrases where a concise statement of information is necessary [5].

At the lexical level, neutral vocabulary is used in its direct meaning: place and date, materials listed, destination, consist of, crates, etc. Book vocabulary is actively used: aforesaid, therewith, etc. Lexical units are monotonous, and words are repeated, since the ambiguous interpretation that is possible in the case of using synonyms is unacceptable.

For example, according to Yu. Fomenko, the linguistic stylistic features of an invoice are clichés, ambiguity, argumentativeness, a clear structure, neutrality of means of expression, standardization, and the absence of authorial techniques [3]. He studies invoices at the lexical level, and she believes that abbreviations prevail at the specified level (Consignment No., VAT, DAP, etc.), terms (total gross weight, commodity code, forwarding agent), established expressions and clichés (the best of my knowledge, particulars furnished by shipper, levy duties on).

Another characteristic feature of customs documents is the use of a significant number of abbreviations: *SAD* (single administrative document), *ATP* (autonomous tariff preference). Common clichés and fixed expressions: *the products named in this document originated in; I hereby declare* [4]. The specified lexical features are intended to save time during the registration of goods, as the information is provided in concise but capacious lexical units.

As noted by linguist Luth imperativeness is one of the main features of the official business style. Most often, this linguopragmatic feature is achieved with the help of indefinite forms of the verb, the infinitive and infinitive constructions:

It is recommended that any user of this document be familiar with ISO 1496-1 (Freight Container Guidance Document, 2014).

Imperativeness is provided by modal verbs **must, shall, to be to**:

Space is provided to list all the items you must declare.

The following markings shall be placed on a freight container with letters at least 13mm in height on the outside of the container (Freight Container Guidance Document, 2014).

In addition, imperativeness is realized through the imperative mode of verbs: *Declare the value of all articles that will remain in the United States.*

Declare all articles on this declaration form and show the value in U.S. dollars. For gifts, please indicate the retail value.

Impersonality and abstractness is another of the main features of customs documents, which is achieved by using:

- passive verbs:

Royalty payments or subsequent proceeds are paid or payable by the purchaser;

The contents of this consignment are fully and accurately described above.

-adverbial constructions:

In the event of the vessel, wharf, warehouse, conveyance, or other cargo being fumigated by order of property constituted authority...;

When shipping hazardous materials, the shipper's certification statement prescribed...

According to Svetlichna conditional constructions are common in official business documents, as they indicate the conditions of offenses and law and order. According to her research, since customs documentation belongs to official and business documents, conditional sentences are used quite often in it [5]:

There shall be no interruption or suspension of transit unless due to circumstances beyond the control of the Assured. Mark with «X» or «RQ» if appropriate

So, the concept and content of linguistic pragmatics is an important factor in the sciences related to the translation process as a whole and the study of the specifics of speech, types of communication, and their application in practice. It was found that customs documents are intended for an accurate and concise description of goods, their characteristics, conditions of sale and transportation, as well as for indicating possible legal consequences in case of non-compliance with certain conditions. Because of this, there is a need for impersonal presentation of information, which is achieved through the use of indefinite forms of verbs, impersonal sentences and passive voice. Paralinguistic features of customs documents are considered. They primarily include the use of modal, imperative and infinitive verbs, which contribute to the imperativeness of the presentation style. At the lexical level, the

maximum accuracy of the presentation is achieved by the use of terms and the complete absence of synonyms that could lead to an ambiguous interpretation of information. Standardization of customs documentation is characterized by the use of clichés and language stamps that speed up the processing of documents at customs.

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